

THE OZONE LAYER DEPLETION IS CONSIDERED TO BE CHALLENGE FOR HUMANITY OVER THE GLOBE

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Abstract: *Ozone-depleting compounds are man-made gases that deplete the ozone layer once they reach it. The ozone layer exists in the high atmosphere and decreases the quantity of ultraviolet radiation that reaches Earth from the sun. Individuals and the environment can be harmed by ultraviolet radiation. I am going to discuss my personal concerns about the ozone layer depletion and its harmful effects to both people and nature. We should protect our Mother Earth from the various super-negative influences. That is why I will explain all the causes and effects in subsequent paragraphs, as well as provide a reliable conclusion.*

Keywords: *Ozone layer depletion, concerns, humanity, deadly effects, motherland, ultraviolet, radiation, health problems, co-operation, only way*

Initially, a question interests me: do you have any warnings about the ozone's next life? Why do I desire to know about this? The reason why these changes not only affect my life but also have the tendency to transform the whole of humanity's lives.

Although ozone is present in low concentrations throughout the atmosphere, the vast majority (about 90%) is found in the stratosphere, a layer 10 to 50 kilometers above the Earth's surface. The ozone layer is essential to life on Earth because it filters away the majority of the sun's harmful ultraviolet rays.

Its molecules operate as a screen against solar radiation. When radiation enters the ozone layer, it travels through the ozone molecules, which are responsible for reflecting some of the radiation back to space, reducing the amount of radiation that reaches us. It is a hole that enables enormous volumes of ultraviolet light to enter and is located at the poles, on the Antarctic continent and the Arctic Ocean, and is

notably large during the spring seasons of both hemispheres, resulting in prolonged summer seasons.

Can you imagine losing your significant other caused by the ozone layer depletion? Because there are some factors leading to deadly diseases such as skin cancers, eye cataracts, and immune deficiency disorders. They are not only negative effects; there are tremendous problems also available. Can you live without food or even other things which are literally part of the whole agriculture system? Why am I going to notice that the main reason is that if we cannot prevent the ozone layer, it will destroy the whole flora and fauna? Because of some deadly radiation, which is an ultraviolet

So you're probably wondering, "What's the deal with me, I'm an innocent in this situation?" Actually, I do not think so. You are the one who is to blame for this problem. Do you have an air conditioning system and a refrigerator? Do you use transport or possibly have a private car? Do you use some kind of cleaning chemical product? Are you fond of foreign products and do not desire to purchase local ones? Absolutely, your answers are all "Yes" like mine. We are all in the same boat, and everyone has a responsibility for this problem. The result is, what should we do? Here are some practical ways to protect and reduce the cause of the hole in the ozone.

Avoid consuming gases that are harmful to the ozone layer owing to their composition or manufacturing process. CFCs (chlorofluorocarbons), halogenated hydrocarbons, methyl bromide, and nitrous oxide are among the most harmful gases.

Reduce your reliance on automobiles. Urban, bicycle, and walking are the best modes of transportation. If you must travel by car, attempt to carpool with others to reduce your carbon footprint and save money.

Use no cleaning agents that are hazardous to the environment or to humans. Many cleaning products contain solvents and corrosive compounds, but you can substitute these risky ingredients with non-toxic alternatives such as vinegar or bicarbonate.

Purchase local items. You not only receive fresh things this way, but you also avoid eating food that has traveled long distances. The medium used to carry that product produces more nitrous oxide as the distance traveled increases.

Maintain air conditioners since breakdowns cause CFCs (**chlorofluorocarbons**) to seep into the atmosphere.

Scientists warned forty years ago that a hole in the ozone layer around the Earth might have major consequences for human health and the environment. This issue is being addressed as a result of a global agreement to prohibit the use of ozone-depleting substances that harm the ozone layer. Scientists are now concerned that the molecules chosen to replace these ozone-depleting chemicals are actually trapping heat within the globe, aggravating the greenhouse effect. Can politicians safeguard the ozone layer while also assisting in the mitigation of climate change?

If I look back over the years, there are a few people who lost their relatives caused by cancer and other types of disease. What a terrible feeling! I am literally here to speak out to the whole of humanity. Why are you continuing to negatively affect the environment and the ozone layer? Last year, my grandma experienced a second time with a cataract. She was able to see the world again after the last operation, but she still has a problem with her right eye. If you were in my grandma's, you could not see well our splendid view of nature and you could not see your children and grandchildren as well. There are more than a thousand individuals who have the same health problem. In addition, this year, one of my aunts passed away because of cancer. Unfortunately, she was only 41 years old.

The most heartbreaking event in my entire life was actually about a girl who is only 3. Once, I went to the hospital due to my practice on the website. I had to write some articles about sick kids. In this case, I came across young children who have different types of diseases. One of the children, as I mentioned at first, had cancer. Why? She was only 3. She wanted to become a doctor. She had a big dream. She wanted to live?! I am shocked. I'm still processing all aspects of my own fault. Please, all my earthlings, we must have cooperated with each other, and the only way to sort out this problem is to be together.

To sum up, we should change our behaviors and the standard of living. Can you commit to your work or study place without catching a bus or other types of transport? Or you can ride a bike, because cycling is the best natural way to go somewhere. It is a really nature-friendly way. Also, you should change your buying habits, such as opting for local products rather than imported ones. Just feeling yourself as a part of nature helps to find your right way. The world is not only ours; our next offspring will carry on living and exploring the universe. I believe that I am with my mother world. I try to change even tiny things. I never stop worrying and explaining the negative effects of what people used to do. Possibly, I will be able to change people's mindsets who live around me. I just ask you to inform others. Please do not ignore them.

REFERENCES:

1. The Ozone Hole-The Montreal Protocol on Substances that Deplete the Ozone Layer". Theozonehole.com. 16 September 1987. Retrieved 2019-05-15.
2. Abarca, J. F.; Casiccia, C. C. (December 2002). "Skin cancer and ultraviolet-B radiation under the Antarctic ozone hole: southern Chile, 1987–2000". *Photodermatol Photoimmunol Photomed*. 18 (6): 294–302. doi:10.1034/j.1600-0781.2002.02782.
3. <https://www.dcceew.gov.au/environment/protection/ozone/ozone-science/ozone-depleting-substances>
4. <https://www.epa.gov/ozone-layer-protection/ozone-depleting-substances>
5. <https://www.canada.ca/en/environment-climate-change/services/air-pollution/issues/ozone-layer/depletion-impacts/substances.html>
6. <https://www.epa.ie/our-services/compliance--enforcement/air/ozone-depleting-substances-ods/>